

Derivation of the Poisson Distribution Part 2

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We have argued in previous notes that one may use a minimal information function G such that $dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$, where c_i is a constant. In other words, one has a set of constraints which allow for multiple $\{p(e_i)\}$ solutions, but by considering differentials and $G = \sum_i h(e_i) p(e_i)$ (or $G = \sum_i h(e_i) p(e_i)^q$ in the Tsallis case), one may obtain a unique distribution. This applies to the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Gaussian, Tsallis and uniform distributions, we argue. Here we try to apply it to the derivation of the Poisson distribution. We note that the maximization approach based on differentials for the MB case yields $\exp(-e_i/T)$ and that one must also consider configurations, i.e. $p \frac{dp}{p}$ in 3-space. We suggest that the $1/n!$ which appears in the Poisson distribution is part of a counting of configurations based on a probability of c power n . One must be careful assigning c as we show.

Maximization of an Entropy Function Based on Differentials of Constraints

In previous notes, we described the method of maximization of entropy $G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$, i.e.

$$dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } h(p(e_i)) = -f(e_i)/T$$

$$\text{Here the usual two constraints are: } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F \quad ((2))$$

This implies that the constraints contain all of the information in the problem and one may obtain a unique maximum entropy by using differentials. We consider the two constraints ((2))

For the MB case, one uses $f(e_i) = e_i$, while for the Gaussian case, $f(e_i) = e_i^2$.

$$\text{Then: } h(p(e_i)) = -f(e_i)/T \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i) \frac{dh}{dp(e_i)} = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad h(p) = \ln(p) \quad ((3))$$

This leads to: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ for the MB case and $p(e_i) = c_1 \exp(-e_i^2/(2\sigma^2))$ for the Gaussian.

In the case of a uniform distribution, one has only one constraint: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and so $\ln(p) = \text{constant}$.

In the Tsallis case, the constraints are: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i p(e_i)^q h(p(e_i))$ and:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -f(e_i)/T \quad \text{with} \quad p(e_i)^q \frac{dh}{dp(e_i)} = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad h(p(e_i)) = 1/(1-q) \{ 1 - p(e_i)^{1-q} \}$$

If $h(p(e_i)) = \ln(p)$ for $q=1$.

Distribution and the Counting of Configurations

As shown above, the MB case yields: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. One, however, cannot simply integrate over dE . Rather, one must consider all possible configurations with the same energy and in the nonrelativistic case this involves: $E = p \cdot p / 2m$. Thus, one must integrate (in spherical co-ordinates) over:

$$4\pi p^2 dp \text{ or } C \sqrt{E} dE \quad ((3))$$

We argue that using the differential approach in the above section, together with the notion of configurations, one may derive the Poisson distribution.

Derivation of the Poisson Distribution

We first begin with the basic idea that there is a rate b_1 (as in Part 1) and the average number of expected events in time t is:

$$b_1 t = B \quad ((4))$$

B is the average number of events for the Poisson distribution, and this is known a priori. Thus, one has a problem with two constraints:

$$\sum_n p(n) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_n n p(n) = B \quad ((5))$$

If one has a minimal information problem, then the approach of the first section should apply, i.e. one should have:

$$p(n) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-c_1 n) \text{ or } c \text{ power } n \quad ((6))$$

The problem is that one does not know c and one must consider the total number of configurations linked with n .

We suggest that n events may occur in a time t . If one breaks t into t/N units where $N \rightarrow \infty$, then one may choose n units out of N i.e.

$$N! / \{ n! (N-n)! \} \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{For } n \text{ finite, } ((7)) \text{ is roughly equivalent to: } 1/n! * N^n \quad ((8))$$

If one sets

$c = B/N$ in $p(n)$ in ((6)), (where $B = b1t$) then one has the overall probability:

$p(n) = C B^n / n!$ From which one finds that $C = \exp(-B)$ as a normalization. ((9))

Thus, we argue that the Poisson distribution is based on the idea of minimal information linked with differentials of an average constraint and $\sum_n p(n) = 1$ as long as one considers the total number of configurations.

Notion of AND = Multiply for Probabilities

In Part 1, we used the idea of an AND situation in probability meaning that one multiplies probabilities. In that way, we wrote $(b1t)^n (1-b1t)^{N-n}$. We note here that the minimal information approach using constraints is consistent with such an AND = multiply procedure. In particular, the minimal information approach yields a power law solution which automatically satisfies the idea of the AND = multiply approach if $f(e_i)$ is the power and $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F$ is the constraint, which is usually the case.

Conclusion

In Part I, we considered a differential equation approach from the literature and a direct factorial approach using the AND= multiply property of probabilities. Here, we suggest that one may use the idea of a minimal entropy $G = -\sum_n p(n) \ln p(n)$ such that $dG = 0 = -\sum_i c_i d p_i$ (constraints). Here there two a priori constraints are: $\sum_n p(n) = 1$ and $\sum_n n p(n) = B$. In other words, the Poisson approach starts with an a priori knowledge of a mean value. This leads to a solution of the form: $p(n)$ proportional to c^n , but one does not know c and must also consider the number of configurations linked to n . We suggest that if a time t is broken into N units then one may choose n of these, i.e. $N! / \{n! (N-n)!\}$ with $N \rightarrow$ infinite. If $c = B/N$, where $B = b1t$, one obtains: $p(n) = C B^n / n!$ from which $C = \exp(-B)$. Thus, we argue that the Poisson distribution is linked with the minimal information associated with constraints, i.e. probability normalization and an average.